

INFLUENCE OF COOLING RATE ON MORPHOLOGICAL AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES

Helen C. Y. Cartledge¹, Caroline A. Baillie² and Yiu Wing Mai¹

¹ Centre for Advanced Materials Technology, Department of Mechanical and Mechatronic Engineering University of Sydney NSW 2006 Australia

² Department of Materials, Imperial College of Science, Technology and Medicine Prince Consort Road, London SW7 2BP, UK

SUMMARY: The influence of cooling rate on the Morphology (crystallinity, phases, transcrystallization) and mechanical properties (transverse flexural tensile, shear strength and modulus, Iosipescu shear strength) has been investigated for both thin films and bulk unidirectional commingled yarn GF/PA6 composites. Cooling condition from fast to slow, -60°C/min, -3°C/min and -1°C/min, were achieved at 1.5 MPa pressure. XRD and DSC techniques were used to analyse the matrix morphology. SEM observation was used to examine the fracture surfaces of the tested samples. The results indicate that a different morphology was found at each different cooling condition. When the cooling rate was shifted from fast to slow, crystallinity and the ratio of α/γ phases were increased in the PA6 matrix associated with enhanced transcrystallinity and interfacial bond. Consequently, the mechanical properties such as tensile and shear strength and elastic modulus, were improved.

KEYWORDS: GF/PA6, cooling rate, crystallinity, α and γ phases, transcrystallinity, interfacial strength, tensile and shear strength, modulus

INTRODUCTION

The mechanical properties of semi-crystalline polymer composites depend on many morphological factors including crystallinity and phases of the matrix and transcrystallinity of the interface, etc, which are determined by thermal processing. However, it is still unclear how phases of the polymers effect the mechanical behaviour of the polymer composites and how to control the morphologies during manufacturing.

The purpose of this study is to find optimum thermal processing condition for thermoplastic composites to enhance the mechanical properties of these composites. GF/PA6 is commonly used in industrial applications and was selected for this study.

EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUE

Materials and Manufacture

Unidirectional GF/PA6 commingled yarn with an E-glass fibre weight fraction of 60% ($V_f=40\%$) was supplied by Toyobo Co., Japan. The consolidating process of the composites

was carried out at 245°C and 1.5 MPa pressure for 10 minutes by using a hydraulic loading hot-press machine. To obtain the different microstructures in the composites, three different cooling processes were conducted, cooled in cold water: -60°C/min, air: -3°C/min and cooled with hot press: -1°C/min with 1.5 MPa pressure. The final dimension of the samples were 200 mm X 200 mm X 4 mm.

Morphological Study

X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) and Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) techniques were used to examine the effect of cooling rate on the morphology of the PA6 matrix. The influence of cooling rate on transcrystallization and microstructure of the GF/PA6 composite thin films was investigated using Polarised Optical Microscopy (POM).

Mechanical Testing

90° three point bending tests were performed according to ASTM 790M-92 to study the influence of cooling rate on the interfacial tensile strength and elastic modulus of the composites. The geometry of the specimens are 80 mm x 10 mm x 4 mm with the fibres perpendicular to the specimen length.

0° double V-notch specimens were used for Iosipescu tests according to ASTM D5379M-93 to measure the interfacial shear strength of GF/PA6 subjected in the different cooling rates. The specimens were cut with fibres parallel to the longitudinal axis-0 degree from the GF/PA6 composite. The geometry of the specimens are 80 mm long, 20 mm wide and 4 mm thick. Two 90° angle notches were cut at the specimen midlength with faces oriented at +45° and -45° to the longitudinal axis. The notches were introduced using a vertical milling machine Pacific FTV-2S with a specially designed parallel fixture. Special care was taken to use optimum cutting rates. A freshly-sharpened cutting tool was used to minimise pre-test damage and produce a sharp notch. The notch tip radius were about 120 µm.

To achieve a pure shear failure in the mid-length of the beam, the width between the two notches tips was reduced to 3 mm instead of the 12 mm which is specified by the ASTM D5379M-93 standard. Both tests were carried out on an Instron 4302 machine at room temperature. SEM observation was used to examine the fracture surfaces of the tested samples.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Morphology

The results from XRD and DSC analysis indicated that crystallinity of the GF/PA6 composites strongly depend on the cooling rates. Figure 1 shows the clear different intensities between the three different cooled GF/PA6 bulk samples in the XRD tests. The area under the sharp peaks represents the crystalline volume in the composites [5]. As it can be seen from the XRD chart, figure 1, that there are two peaks appearing in all of the three cooling rates samples, α and γ phases.

In general, an orderly packed crystalline polymer has higher density than that of a loosely and random packed amorphous polymer. The more crystalline structure formed in the polymers, the more energy should be needed to damage the high density polymers.

Fig. 1: X-ray chart of GF/PA6 composites subjected in three different cooling conditions

The physical properties of polymers are dominated by intermolecular hydrogen bonding and chain packing. The hydrogen bonding angle in the α crystal is bigger than that of the γ crystal so that the α chain is straighter and longer than that of γ chain. α chains are packed tighter than that of γ . Thus, the density of the α phase is higher than that of the γ phase. Therefore, when damaging an equal volume of the α and γ crystalline matrix, α phase should need more energy than that of γ phase. Table 1 shows the crystallinity and ratio of α/γ phases versus cooling rate.

Table 1: Ratio of α and γ phases and crystallinity of GF/PA6 verse cooling rate

Samples Cooling Rate	Ratio of α/γ Phases	Crystallinity of $\alpha+\gamma$ Phases
-1°C/min	27	37%
-3°C/min	2.6	20%
-60°C/min	1.2	17%

The Polarised Optical Microscopy (POM) study of the GF/PA6 thin films shows that there are columnar spherulites growing along the glass fibre in the slowest cooled samples. It may be a transcrystalline region between the matrix and fibre. The columnar spherulite structures disappeared with increased cooling rate in the samples.

Mechanical Properties

Returning now to the mechanical tests. It can be seen that the tensile and shear strengths of the GF/PA6 composites are dramatically affected by the cooling rate. The flexural elastic modulus are effected as well. In table 2 it is shown that reducing the cooling rate lead to enhancing the strengths and modulus.

Table 2: The flexural maximum tensile strength and modulus versus cooling rate in 90 ° three point bending test, ultimate failure shear strength versus cooling rate in 0 ° Iosipescu tests.

Samples cooling rate	Flexural Test σ_{\max} (MPa)	Iosipescu Test τ_{ult} (MPa)	Flexural Test E (GPa)
-1°C/min	42.89	120	4.3
-3°C/min	33.79	91	3.5
-60°C/min	25.58	79	2.4

The maximum tensile stress, σ_{\max} , obtained from 90° flexural test reflects the tensile strength of the interfacial bonding. The ultimate shear stress, τ_{ult} which was obtained from 0° Iosipescu test, occurs at the midlength of the specimen and between the two notch tips. It reflects the shear strength of the GF/PA6 composite interfacial bonding. The modulus reflects the stiffness of PA6 matrix. Therefore, with increasing cooling rate interfacial bond in tension and shear is reduced.

Effect of Morphology on Fracture Mechanisms

The SEM observations show that the rupture surfaces of the flexural and Iosipescu specimens occur between the fibre and the matrix (see figs 2 and 3). Figure 2a and 2b show the fracture surfaces of the GF/PA6 samples subjected in -1°C/min and -60°C/min, respectively, at the lowest point of the midspan in flexural test. Figure 3a and 3b show the fracture surfaces of the GF/PA6 samples subjected in -1°C/min and -60°C/min, respectively, in the midplane of the midspan in Iosipescu test.

It can be seen that there is matrix tears and interfacial debonding in the fracture surfaces. There is more resin adhering to the fibres for the slower cooling rate than that of fast cooling. Thus, it can be inferred that the interfacial strength is stronger for the slowest cooling samples, verifying the previous results. It was also found in the SEM photos, figure 2a and figure 3a, that there is a large amount of fibre breakage appearing in slowest cooled samples. It should be attributed to the strong interfacial bond transferring the force to the fibres.

A high crystallinity and large amount of α phase formed in the slow cooling samples, it gives the matrix higher density and strength which contributes to the maximum tensile stress, σ_{\max} , and modulus in flexural tests. The slow cooling leads to the formation of a transcrystalline layer which gives the composite strong interfacial bond and contributes to the ultimate shear stress, τ_{ult} , in Iosipescu tests and maximum tensile stress, σ_{\max} , in flexural tests.

Fig. 2a: SEM photo of midspan lowest point fracture surface from flexural test, -1 °C/min cooling rate sample

Fig. 2b: SEM photo of midspan lowest point fracture surface from flexural test, -60 °C/min cooling rate sample

Fig. 3a: SEM photo of midplane fracture surface from Iosipescu test, -1 °C/min cooling rate sample

Fig. 3b: SEM photo of midplane fracture surface from Iosipescu test, -60 °C/min cooling rate sample

CONCLUSIONS

The results obtained in this research lead to the following conclusions.

- 1) The crystallinity of PA6 strongly depends on cooling rate during thermal processing. Slow cooling leads to higher crystallinity and more α crystals formed than fast cooling. The increased α phase leads to higher density of PA6 matrix.
- 2) The transcristallinity of GF/PA6 strongly depends on the cooling rate too. Slow cooling leads to the formation of a transcristalline layer.
- 3) It is assumed that the high density matrix and strong interfacial bonding between fibre and matrix indicated by Iosipescu, flexural tests and SEM observation result in better mechanical properties in the slow cooled GF/PA6 composite samples than that of fast cooled samples.
- 4) This is considered to be due to the slow cooling leads to 37% crystallinity and large amount α phase formed in the PA6 matrix which give the composite a harder matrix and higher tensile strength than that of fast cooling. It also improves the interfacial bonding condition and gives the composite higher interfacial strength than that of fast cooling.

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